

IMPLEMENTATION OF COMMUNITY BASED TOURISM PRINCIPLES IN PINGE TOURISM VILLAGE, TABANAN, BALI

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Abstract: The limited ability of human resources to be competitive, independent, and innovative in Pinge Tourism Village is an obstacle to local community expectations of how a community-based tourism principle can be implemented as expected. Therefore, even though it is managed directly by the community, the development of the Pinge Tourism Village must of course always be directed and evaluated whether the concept of community-based tourism implemented by the community is ideal with the principles of community-based tourism. Based on this, it is important for researchers to conduct an analysis of the principles of community-based tourism in Pinge Tourism Village.

In this study, qualitative data analysis was used. The conclusion of this study is that in general, Pinge Tourism Village has implemented almost all the principles of developing community-based tourism in the economic, social, cultural, environmental, and political dimensions well. Suggestions that can be given by researchers are suggestions for managers or tourism-aware groups, the community, and the role of local governments in pursuing several aspects of community-based tourism principles that still need to be optimized.

Keywords: Implementation, Community Based Tourism, Tourism Village.

I. INTRODUCTION

Alternative tourism trends begin with fluctuations in tourist visits to conventional forms of tourism. Basically, this trend appears along with the growing awareness of tourists and tourism actors about the importance of environmental sustainability, culture, and community empowerment. Significantly this trend shifted the mass form to the special. One form of alternative tourism trends, namely Tourism Villages. The concept of Community Based Tourism emerged because of the importance of the role of local communities in the development of a tourism destination, so that it became the driving force for the emergence of new trends in the development of tourism based on local communities. According to Suansri (2003) there are five principles which are the main aspects of the development of Community Based Tourism covering social, economic, cultural, environmental, and political dimensions.

Pinge Tourism Village became the first tourist village in Tabanan Regency which was inaugurated as a tourist village based on Tabanan Regent Decree No. 337 of 2004. However, the management and structuring program at that time was still not optimally developed by both the government and local communities. The local community began to take the initiative in structuring the village in 2011 and was moved to develop the Pinge Tourism Village after going through a seven-year vacuum. During the vacuum of Pinge Tourism Village for seven years, the management and arrangement of the village at that time was dominated by the village elite. The domination of the elite in the Pinge Tourism Village is divided into two elite groups, where the inclusive elite group is an elite category that is relatively willing to share

knowledge and experience while the exclusive elite group is an elite category that accumulates capital in the Pinge Tourism Village or tourism domain and owns it exclusively (Adikampana and Pujani, 2015). The typical habit of exclusive elite groups is that they view local communities as subordinates, based on "command-ordered" interactions because these groups come from retired government bureaucratic officials, while the inclusive elite group comes from retired private professionals who are accustomed to working with teams, so the relationships that are formed are more in the form of a work partner (Adikampana and Pujani, 2015).

The inclusive elite group has a desire to involve the community, has a vision of developing small-scale rural tourism that does not conflict with local traditions and culture, and targets quality tourist visits. On the other hand, the exclusive elite group is dominating and monopolizes the network of relations, does not care about community involvement, and has a vision of developing large-scale tourism by attracting as many tourists visits as possible regardless of whether this is contrary to environmental conditions or local traditions and culture. The existence of differences in interests, expectations between inclusive elite groups and exclusive elites for the type of Pinge Tourism Village Management gave rise to dissociative social interactions, namely elite conflicts, and the sparse social cohesiveness of the community during the vacuum period.

The form of elite dominance in Pinge Tourism Village at that time was shown in the centralization of the economic benefits of homestay rentals which were mostly obtained by the village elite. This is not without reason, where the homestays available at the beginning of the Pinge Tourism Village Development were only 20 rooms in five local community houses and of the five homestays belonging to the village elite were considered to have better capital capabilities and were more comfortable for tourists.

The quality of Human Resources in Pinge Tourism Village is currently classified as still not optimal, which is limited by structural limitations. This is because there is still a lack of community capacity building and the understanding base of Pinge Tourism Village Managers currently does not come from the tourism sector. The concept of community based Pinge Tourism Village Management that is currently being implemented is expected to be analyzed optimally and can provide improvement efforts in the form of CBT which is still less than ideal with the principles of developing community-based tourism. Therefore, it is interesting to analyze and it is important to conduct research related to the Application of Community Based Tourism Principles in Pinge Tourism Village, Tabanan, Bali. The research aims to provide an explanation and description of how to analyze the suitability of the implementation of developing community-based tourism that is implemented in the Pinge Tourism Village, as well as the benefits of research to reveal the forms of implementing community-based tourism in the Pinge Tourism Village as well as efforts to optimize community-based tourism.

The concepts used to answer the problem formulation in this research are the concept of tourism (The Ecotourism Society, 1990), the concept of tourist attraction (Pitana, 2009), the concept of a tourist village (Priasukmana and Mulyadin, 2001), the concept of community-based tourism (Suansri, 2003), the concept of social interaction (Wulansari, 2009) and the concept of participation (Cohen and Uphoff, 1979).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A review of previous research is very important to determine the position of the research carried out with what has been done. The first research study has the same research locus with the title "Potential of Pinge Village as a Tourism Village in Marga District, Tabanan Regency" by Tabing Geovani and Ida Bagus Suryawan (2014). The second research is research entitled "Local Community Integration Model in Rural Tourism Destination Planning" by I Made Adikampana and Luh Putu Kerti Pujani in 2015. This research discusses the existence of two elite typologies, namely inclusive and exclusive in Pinge Tourism Village. The third research has the same focus with the title "Implementation of Community Based Tourism in Lamalera B Tourism Village in Supporting Estate Tourism in East Nusa Tenggara" by Sari Bandaso Tandilino and Pasifikus Mala Meko (2020). The difference between the first and second research studies with current research can be seen from the focus of research which is more directed at the potential of Pinge Village, and the integration of local communities, while this research focuses on the application of community-based tourism. The third research has the same research focus, namely the application of community-based tourism, but the research location is different.

III. RESEARCH METHODS

Pinge Tourism Village is in Baru Village, Marga District, Tabanan Regency. Pinge tourist village is located at an altitude of 500 meters above sea level, so the air temperature of Pinge Tabanan Tourism Village is quite cool, and filled with lush tropical plants, as well as terraced rice fields ready to present an amazing and attractive charm. Heading to Pinge Tourism Village can be reached by land from Denpasar City about 37 kilometers with a travel time of 1 hour 9 minutes, and the distance from Ngurah Rai International Airport is 48 Kilometers with a travel time of 1 hour 23 minutes.

The scope of the research is a limitation of the scope of the problem, so that the direction of the data from the research becomes clear. The scope of the problems in this research are the forms of application of the principles of community-based tourism in the Pinge Tourism Village. The implementation of community-based tourism in Pinge Tourism Village, the data aspects are the application of CBT on the economic dimension, the application of CBT on the social dimension, the application of CBT on the environmental dimension, the application of CBT on the political dimension, the application of CBT on the cultural dimension.

This study uses qualitative data types (Sugiyono, 2014) and quantitative data (Sugiyono, 2014). Sources of data in this study are primary and secondary data sources (Sugiyono, 2014). Data collection techniques used include interviews (Sugiyono, 2014), the interview process is carried out with interview guidelines with managers, pokdarwis, and the community in Pinge Tourism Village. Observation (Sugiyono, 2014) to directly ascertain whether the data obtained is in accordance with the real situation in the field. This study also uses documentation techniques (Sugiyono, 2014) to obtain data on the number of visits, data on the number of homestays, data on the number of residents from secondary data sources. The data analysis technique used is interactive model analysis as stated by Miles and Huberman (2014) through the stages of data collection, data reduction, data presentation, and drawing conclusions.

IV. RESULT

A. Pinge Tourism Village Overview

Pinge Tourism Village is in Marga District, Tabanan Regency with an area of 145 hectares and a population of 829 people with 165 families (KK). Most people's livelihoods in Pinge Tourism Village are farmers with a total of 699 people, the rest work as entrepreneurs 107 people, civil servants and 23 employees. The number of businesses related to tourism developed by the community are 75 homestay rooms, four food stalls, small industries of leather, wood, plaiting, food, metal, pottery, ceramics, weaving, cloth, as many as four. Tourism supporting infrastructure in Pinge Tourism Village includes adequate meeting places, art performances with beautiful panoramas, composting buildings/depots supporting the Green and Clean Bali program, as well as the "Laduma" rest area.

Table I: The Geographical Location Of Pinge Village

Borderline	Area
North	Banjar Tegeh
East	Tukad Yeh Kajang
South	Tegal Sepit
West	Pangkung Bangka
Area Range : 145 Ha Population : 829 Families : 165 KK	

Source: Pinge Tourism Village Management Documentation, 2021

The participation of the local community in maintaining local wisdom, Tri Hita Karana and the enthusiastic attitude of the Pinge Tourism Village community are still reflected in the spirit of cooperation in preserving the environment and building their village to this day. In March 2021, Pinge Tourism Village has inaugurated a rest area for tourists, which is named "Laduma" which means former rice field. In the future, Laduma is planned as a place to carry out workshops, training or education activities involving tourists and the participation of the village community. The source of funds and the management of obtaining tourism benefits from the Pinge Tourism Village are managed by Baga Utsaha Padruwen Traditional Village (BUPDA) to date.

B. The Potential of Tourist Attractions in the Pinge Tourism Village

The potential of the Pinge Tourism Village is divided into natural, cultural, and artificial potential, including the following:

1. Natural Potential:

- a. Pacung Subak and Bebaluan Subak
- b. The scenery of the village environment is natural and clean

2. Cultural Potential:

- a. Traditional dance performances, such as: Leko Dance and Bumbung Gebyog.
- b. Historical relics, namely: Pura Natar Jemeng
- c. Religious ceremony
- d. The structure of the house and the pattern of community life are based on the value of the local wisdom of Tri Hita Karana where it is not permitted to change the function of space for any reason or purpose.
- e. The arrangement of the trail at Jaba Pura Puseh, in the corridor of Pinge Tourism Village, along the corridor as a form of green open space planted with plants or ornamental plants by the local community.

3. Artificial Potency:

- a. Trekking Path

Opening of Trekking routes across rice fields, rivers, forests, and the Natar Jemeng Temple with a three km long path outside the settlement without risking damage to rice fields, rivers, or forests

- b. Rest area

The construction of a rest area named "Laduma" as a form of utilization of vacant land used for rice fields belonging to the Traditional Village. Laduma is facilitated with four gazebos so that tourists can relax while enjoying the natural scenery in the village. Laduma is also expected to become a center for activities such as workshops, training, and other activities.

C. Implementation of Community Based Tourism Principles in Pinge Tourism Village

The implementation of community-based tourism in Pinge Tourism Village began to be seen clearly in practice in 2017 where local community houses began to increase from previously there were only five to 16 houses that could be used for tourists with an interest in studying art, culture, and nature with the community (Astawa, I.P, 2017). Technically in 2017, the distribution of tourists who want to stay is carried out proportionally to all community houses in Pinge Tourism Village that have homestays (Dewi, Paramadhyaksa and Prajnawrdhi, 2017). Based on the results of interviews with village managers, decision making, and policies are carried out on a bottom-up basis based on the aspirations of the people in Pinge Tourism Village to managers for fair and balanced economic equity.

This analysis is carried out at the same time clarifying how the practice of community-based tourism is related to elite conflict in the Pinge Tourism Village. In analyzing the application of community-based tourism in Pinge Tourism Village, researchers collected data through observations and interviews based on the aspects of the data to be explored, including the form of implementing community based tourism dimensions including economic, social, cultural, environmental, and political dimensions. Through the results of observations and interviews, the following results were obtained:

1. Economic Dimension

Regarding tourism, the economic sector can be an indicator of the development of an area that becomes a tourism destination or has a tourist attraction. In the indicator of the existence of funds for community development, it was found that the source of funds for the development and development of the Pinge Tourism Village came from the BUPDA (Baga Utsaha Padruwen Desa Adat). These funds have been realized in several developments in the village, one of which is the construction of a rest area. The creation of job opportunities for the surrounding community is shown by the presence of a cooking and dancing class instructor from the Merta Dewi group, a local guide.

One of the sources of income for local people is processed coconut oil which is sold for Rp. 15.000,-/bottle. The existence of agronomic activities favored by tourists such as plowing the fields, preparing seeds, planting seeds, and harvesting the cultivation of local communities also contributes in the form of wages to breeders or farmers ranging from Rp. 20,000, - up to Rp. 100,000, - by participating in these activities. The income from providing local culinary food ranges from Rp. 50.000,- up to Rp. 100.000,-.

Every tourist who comes on a tour for the first time and wants to stay at the Pinge Tourism Village will certainly be directed to the Pinge Tourism Village Manager first. After that, the Pinge Tourism Village Manager will determine and decide which homestay to be placed in. This is done as an effort to equalize the local community's economy. Currently there are 75 units of homestay rooms that are managed and spread in the homes of local people under the auspices of the manager with the price per night is Rp. 150,000/person up to Rp. 250.000/person where the price includes tracking. As much as 6% of the contribution of income from homestays is channeled to the Pinge Tourism Village Manager which will then be channeled to BUPDA.

2. Social Dimension

An increase in community pride in the Pinge Tourism Village is shown by the pokdarwis competition, the involvement of tourists who feel happy with the cleanliness of the village by participating in village cleaning services, the community also feels proud of the involvement of tourists who want to follow the routine of farming, plowing the fields and learning to cook traditional food. . The improvement in the quality of life of the community is indicated by approximately 10% to 15% of the productive age community in Pinge Village currently graduating from high school / vocational / equivalent and more directed to work in the craft sector, cruise ships, and tourism. The number of productive age people who graduated from D3, D4 and S1 are still with the same percentage composition, if 10% to 15% leads to various different fields such as: Tourism, STAN, management, agriculture, animal husbandry and medicine. In addition, with training such as housekeeping, guiding, website creation, counseling on the potential of Subak, training in making organic waste processing tools and English classes where the teaching staff is five people from the community itself for children in the Pinge Tourism Village. .

The fair division of roles between gender and age is indicated by the formation of women's farmer groups whose role is to provide education on how to cook traditional food to tourists. The existence of Sekaa Teruna is also involved in providing innovative development ideas, one of which is planning for making photo spots. The role of women is also not only working in the kitchen, but also being able to work like men in the fields as farmers (domestic and public). Likewise, the role of cooking can also be carried out by men in the Pinge Tourism Village. The strengthening of community organizations is shown by the existence of Pokdarwis (Tourism Awareness Groups) with group divisions according to the seven elements of SAPTA PESONA where members are selected through deliberation based on traditional meetings according to individual competence. The Pokdarwis meeting in Pinge Village was held technically informally while working in the fields and during free time. Free time is referred to as after completing community service and while drinking coffee.

3. Cultural Dimension

The condition of the people in Pinge Tourism Village before the tourism activities were mostly farmers. After the development of tourism, local people continue to carry out agricultural activities (cultivating crops, plowing fields) and cultivating plants which are a tourist attraction for tourists every time they visit Pinge Tourism Village. This also creates additional income for the local community. The indicator that encourages people to respect different cultures is shown by the positive interaction that is built between the community and tourists where the community will always be involved in all tourist tourism activities and vice versa, one of which is during agronomic activities. The stakeholders also always provide socialization for the community not to consider other cultures to be inferior to their own culture and to be willing to learn about foreign cultures without losing the local culture. Local communities in Pinge Tourism Village are generally also very open and friendly in welcoming tourists because for the people of Pinge Tourism Village, tourists are considered part of the family.

The development of cultural exchange is carried out by holding art performances such as Leko Dance, Wali Pendet Dance, Bumbung Gebyog. Tourists also could learn the dance by taking a dance class at Pinge Tourism Village. In addition, tourists also could study

Table II: Number of Tourist Visits in Pinge Tourism Village (2011-2017)

No.	Year	Tourist
1.	2011	1.066
2.	2012	1.141
3.	2013	859
4.	2014	1.152
5.	2015	1.634
6.	2016	1.822
7.	2017	798
Tourist		8.472

Source: Pokdarwis Desa Wisata Pinge, 2018

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the level of tourist visits continues to increase until it is confirmed that in 2018-2019 there are about 1500 to 3500 tourists visiting Pinge Tourism Village. The pattern of tourist visits to the Pinge Tourism Village is also erratic, where there are people staying overnight and just visiting. Trash cans are provided in every community yard, every street corner, Bale Banjar yard, Laduma yard, and in every food stall in the village area. In the management of organic waste such as weathering the remains of plants, animals, and kitchen waste in the Pinge Tourism Village, the local community has been very aware of it. The Pinge Tourism Village community manages organic waste as compost in the yard around their residence using a composter.

Increased awareness of the need for conservation is shown by the appeal that was ratified by Perbup Tbn No. 15 of 2017 as well as village regulations related to the arrangement of telajakans by not carrying out physical development in the telajakan area. With this regulation, the people in Pinge Tourism Village create their own creations by utilizing clean, neat trends planted with plants that can beautify the face of residential corridors. There is strict follow-up and control by village officials if development violations are found in the telajakan zone and the sangkep (village meeting) which provides direction on the importance of the existence and cleanliness of the telajakan as a Green Open Space (RTH). Krama subak in Pinge Tourism Village was formed to support the conservation of the potential of subak and carry out routine ceremonies such as mapag toya and mantenin ceremonies. As a form of increasing awareness, the people in Pinge Tourism Village also inaugurated the construction of biodiesel, an environmentally friendly energy that utilizes solar system power.

5. Political dimension

Community involvement in decision-making means that the community can have wishes and hopes that can be issued especially for the benefit of tourism development so that later it can be used as input for further tourism development. Indicators of increased participation from local residents, can be seen from the activeness of the community willing to join in the organization that manages Pinge Tourism Village. Likewise, the decision-making process is carried out on the aspirations of the people in the Pinge Tourism Village which are then realized together with the village manager. The holding of formal or informal meetings at the Pinge Tourism Village aims to discuss the program of activities and development that will be carried out.

The Sekaa Teruna group also participated in contributing ideas (participation of thoughts) in the form of planning to make several photo spots in the Pinge Tourism Village area. The decision to plan and implement an activity program in the Pinge Tourism Village is open and based on the results of community consultations, where the community can provide suggestions, input, or reject a program. One of the development programs agreed upon and approved by deliberation, namely: the construction of vacant land located in the north of the village as a rest area named "Laduma" and the construction of environmentally friendly biosolar energy. In the future, Laduma will also be used as a community training center and workshop.

The community is also involved in the implementation of the program, in the form of participation in the form of mutual assistance by opening tracking lines for the construction of facilities and infrastructure, Laduma, gazebos, cleaning of tracking lines and community service. In the form of funding, it is also carried out voluntarily by the community and then contributed to the manager for maximum improvement and development in the village. The community in Pinge Tourism Village is also included in the implementation of trainings that are accompanied by educational institutions and from BUMN, such as training on making organic waste processing equipment, guiding training, and housekeeping. The agreement to equalize the acquisition of economic benefits is also a form of community participation.

The form of agreement in the Pinge Tourism Village is an agreement to equalize the acquisition of economic benefits in the provision of homestays with a fair determination from the village manager every time there are tourists who want to stay. With a fair determination from the manager based on equality of opportunity for acquisition, it shows that the elite conflict in Pinge Tourism Village has been accommodated for the equal distribution of economic benefits between village elites and non-village elites. The agreement to obtain economic benefits fairly is also felt by the women's farmer groups from cooking class activities, and agronomic activities. People in the Pinge Tourism Village can also use organic waste processing equipment in their respective homes and use them in their daily lives. There are benefits obtained by the community from the biodiesel development program as environmentally friendly energy, namely: the management of solar electricity is used as a place of education in the Pinge Tourism Village.

In the evaluation activities, the community in Pinge Tourism Village was also involved in a supervisory group that empowers local pecalang in maintaining security, supervision, and routine maintenance carried out by the community. The community in Pinge Tourism Village also monitors performance and is invited to hold an evaluation meeting if there are discrepancies or irregularities so as to minimize negative impacts in the future. One of the violations that occurred was: the construction of a shop in the tread zone by one of the residents' houses. This was finally resolved by deliberation by the community in Pinge Tourism Village.

Indicators of increasing the power of the wider community carried out by Pinge Tourism Village are: the existence of partnerships with ITDC (Indonesia Tourism Development Corporation), Udayana University, Bali State Polytechnic, partnerships with Banks (BTN, BRI, BNI, Mandiri) Semen Indonesia, Pertamina , other SOEs, and counseling about the potential of subak in service activities from the National Education University. The form and results of the collaboration carried out by the Pinge Tourism Village, in the form of: guiding training, housekeeping training, assistance in the form of building 6 sink units, building a TIC (Tourist Information Center), structuring angkul-angkul in front of the house, making kukul poles (which means profit.), additional construction of lighting lamps in village areas, and trash bins.

Some forms or results of other partnerships are: the existence of a help channel for implementing health protocols, namely: 200 masks, 115 hand sanitizers, 12 liquid soaps, assistance provided by Udayana University in various studies, as well as making proposals.

The service and training is also a form of partnership, namely: training in the manufacture of organic waste processing equipment, training to increase skills in processing and serving food to increase tourist visits, Biosolar development as an environmentally friendly energy that utilizes solar power in the "Laduma" rest area.

D. Implementation of Community Based Tourism Principles in the less-ideal Pinge Tourism Village

The following are some of the practices of community based tourism that are still less than ideal and optimally carried out by Pinge Tourism Village as follows:

1. The application of the principle of community based tourism in the Pinge Tourism Village on the economic dimension, there are still several indicators that have not been maximally implemented, namely: minimal and limited funds so that planning and development such as photo spots, structuring a one Km tracking path to the north of the village must postponed. In addition, because of the basic negotiations between travel agents and tourists regarding the price of tour packages offered at Pinge Tourism Village, there is no fixed price standard for the provision of homestays or full day tour/stay packages.
2. The application of the principle of community based tourism in Pinge Tourism Village on the social dimension, there are still several indicators that have not been maximally implemented, namely:
 - a. The quality of human resources in mastering science and technology and making village websites is still less than optimal, as can be seen from the absence of an official website for the Pinge Tourism Village to date as well as;
 - b. There are no experts who fully master the management of financial funds appropriately and effectively.
3. The application of the principle of community based tourism in Pinge Tourism Village on the environmental dimension there are still several indicators that have not been maximally implemented, namely:
 - a. The capacity of the Pinge Tourism Village is limited only if the number of available homestays has been fulfilled so that there is no set limit for the maximum number of tourist visits in the Pinge Tourism Village.
 - b. Pinge Tourism Village also still has not done the sorting of inorganic waste.

E. Efforts to Apply Community Based Tourism Principles in Pinge Tourism Village

The effort to apply the CBT principle is to fulfill the indicators that have not been optimally implemented in the Pinge Tourism Village, namely:

1. Solutions that can be done to overcome the application of the principle of community based tourism in the less than optimal social dimensions are:
 - a. Studying the management of village funds and cooperating with local capital investors or wider entrepreneurs in overcoming community development funds which are still limited to the economic dimension and the role of educational institutions to assist local communities.
 - b. Running a flexible pricing strategy by considering competitors' prices, determining customer value, market profile, taking into account product costs, operational costs, selling costs and more focused on profit quality.
 - c. Provide detailed information about tour packages and prices offered in promotional media such as Facebook and Instagram. The management and monitoring are also carried out periodically to find out the feedback obtained.
2. Solutions that can be done to overcome the application of the principle of community based tourism in a less than optimal social dimension, namely: Pokdarwis proposes to academics from educational institutions that have assisted or not for science and technology training, making websites that are more intensive in nature to strengthen quality and quantity HR capabilities while at the same time overcoming the absence of experienced professional human resources in the field of science and technology in Pinge Tourism Village.
3. Solutions that can be done to overcome the application of the principle of community based tourism in environmental dimensions that are less than optimal are:
 - a. Conducting AMDAL studies, carrying capacity area management control regulations. In addition, it can also involve the central/regional government, as well as tourism consultants in calculating the limit on the maximum number of visits in one day based on the area and actual capacity management (number of existing management officers with the required number of management officers).
 - b. The formation of a special group for the environmental care movement in overcoming the lack of balance in the carrying capacity area and the arrangement of inorganic waste sorting on the principle of CBT in the environmental dimension.
 - c. Provide education to the public about the importance of awareness in sorting waste by type. In this case, a companion role is also needed to facilitate technologically how to process inorganic waste into useful things such as fuel and recycled products that can be used or sold to tourists.

V. CONCLUSION

The practice of community based tourism that has been carried out has been able to resolve the problems of elite conflict in the Pinge Tourism Village and achieve political integration that leads to the form of social interaction in the form of accommodation. This is done with the distribution of economic benefits in providing homestays carried out by the management together with the community, as well as a fair division of roles.

In the economic dimension, local communities get additional income from processed products and activities with tourists, as well as opening up employment opportunities from tourism activities in Pinge Tourism Village. Funds for village development and management are also sourced from BUPDA.

On the social dimension, it is indicated by an increase in the quality of life of the people in the Pinge Tourism Village in terms of education and work levels. The fair distribution of age and gender is also demonstrated by the participation of sekaa cadets and the formation of the Merta Dewi Group.

In the cultural dimension, it is indicated by the form of socialization with the community to respect each other's different cultures, not demeaning other people's cultures or leaving their own culture. The culture to always be on-time, clean and the use of advanced technology is also a form of positive cultural exchange carried out at Pinge Tourism Village.

In the environmental dimension, there are awig-awig (regulations) and policies that are closely held by the community in Pinge Tourism Village, one of which is that they are not allowed to build anything that crosses the plug limit. The

processing of organic waste carried out by the community in Pinge Tourism Village is used as compost in the fields and yards of the house.

In the political dimension, the form of deliberation is the thing that is most highlighted in Pinge Tourism Village. Decision making, participation in ideas, involvement of all members of the community, from planning to supervision are carried out fairly. The partnership was also carried out by Pinge Tourism Village to expand relations and assistance in the form of knowledge, training and experience with ITDC, Bali State Polytechnic, Udayana University, and several other SOEs.

However, the implementation of the principle of community based tourism carried out by the Pinge Tourism Village still has several things that are less than optimal or ideal, such as minimal funds, lack of mastery of science and technology, and the absence of sorting inorganic waste.

The suggestions in this study were submitted to the managers and pokdarwis of the Pinge Tourism Village, the Pinge Tourism Village community, and the Government and BUPDA, namely for managers, managers can consider increasing cooperative relationships with existing educational institutions, integrated communication with the community and improving human resource capacity in a more sustainable manner.

For the people of the Pinge Tourism Village, it is hoped that they can continue to be critical in taking new opportunities and innovations related to tourism activities in the village, as well as being able to convey and appreciate the aspirations that are carried out together in every routine meeting.

The government and BUPDA are expected to provide assistance in the form of special training to improve human resource capabilities, and to build commitment and good relations with the community in Pinge Tourism Village.

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